

1 Integrating Global Canopy Height Models with Satellite Data for 2 Improved Forest Inventory in Ukraine

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13

14 Abstract

15 Accurate forest monitoring in Ukraine faces unprecedented challenges due to ongoing Russian aggression and
16 limited access to traditional inventory methods, requiring robust satellite-based alternatives for National Forest
17 Inventory operations. This study develops a comprehensive framework integrating state-of-the-art canopy
18 height models with registered multi-sensor satellite data to achieve airborne LiDAR-comparable accuracy in
19 forest structural parameter estimation.

20

21 Here, we evaluated six canopy height models (CHM) against in-situ National Forest Inventory (NFI)
22 measurements of canopy height across Ukraine. The most recent European-scale CHM by Pauls et al. (2025)
23 demonstrated superior performance with $R^2 = 0.68$ and $RMSE = 4.65$ m. Using this CHM as input alongside
24 registered optical (Sentinel-2) and radar (Sentinel-1, ALOS PALSAR-2) observations, we developed a
25 machine learning framework testing 20 algorithms to address whether satellite-derived canopy height enhances
26 forest structural parameter estimation and whether country-trained models match regionally specific
27 approaches. Feature importance analysis revealed CHM-derived height as the dominant predictor (45-60%),
28 followed by Sentinel-2 shortwave infrared bands and vegetation indices. This approach achieved relative
29 RMSE values of 8.8-12.3% across four forest structural parameters: growing stock volume ($R^2 = 0.77$), basal

30 area ($R^2 = 0.68$), stand age ($R^2 = 0.53$), and diameter at breast height ($R^2 = 0.48$). Performance improvements
31 of 49-144% were observed compared to models without height information. The framework successfully
32 generates wall-to-wall forest inventory maps with robust transferability across diverse forest conditions. This
33 research establishes satellite-based forest inventory as a viable alternative for data-scarce environments
34 worldwide.

35

36 **Keywords:** forest inventory, machine learning, canopy height model, remote sensing

37 **Introduction**

38 The assessment of forest resources in Ukraine faces a unique dual challenge: a historical lack of comprehensive
39 statistical data and severe modern operational constraints. Unlike many European nations with long-
40 established National Forest Inventories (NFI), Ukraine only initiated its first sample-based NFI cycle in 2021.
41 Consequently, even prior to the escalation of the conflict, the country lacked a completed, spatially consistent
42 national inventory baseline. This structural data gap was significantly compounded by the Russian aggression.
43 It is crucial to note that while the full-scale invasion in 2022 expanded the zone of inaccessibility, parts of the
44 Donetsk and Luhansk regions, along with the entire Crimean Peninsula, have been inaccessible for any ground-
45 based monitoring since 2014. Traditional inventory methods, which rely heavily on field sampling and airborne
46 data collection, have thus been impossible in these territories for over a decade, and are now severely limited
47 across approximately 20% of the country due to mining and active combat. In this context, remote sensing
48 offers more than just a safety measure; it provides the only viable means to generate the complete national-
49 scale baseline that the interrupted NFI could not deliver.

50

51 The integration of remote sensing into forest monitoring is not a recent development; the effort to estimate
52 regional wood volume and biomass using satellite imagery combined with ancillary data has been recognized
53 as a critical approach for decades (Fazakas et al., 1999). However, these pioneering efforts were often
54 constrained by the saturation of optical signals in high-biomass stands, highlighting the ongoing need for
55 improved three-dimensional structural information. To overcome this saturation problem, accurate vertical
56 structure information is crucial. Structural variables have long been incorporated into forest attribute modeling,
57 with numerous studies demonstrating their critical importance for predicting forest structure, biomass,
58 productivity, and species composition. While the use of canopy height as a robust allometric proxy is well
59 established in the literature, its operational application within the specific context of Ukrainian forest systems
60 has remained underexplored. In this targeted environment, canopy height acts as the critical third dimension,
61 remaining sensitive even in dense, multi-layered canopies where optical indices saturates.

62

63 Initial applications of satellite-based forest assessment in Ukraine have demonstrated significant potential,
64 providing the first spatially explicit estimation of forest resources using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time series
65 (Myroniuk et al., 2024). However, these pioneering efforts relied primarily on multispectral optical imagery.

66 While effective for mapping forest cover, optical data suffers from signal saturation in high biomass stands,
67 where spectral response becomes insensitive to further accumulation of growing stock volume (Lu, 2006). To
68 overcome this saturation problem, accurate vertical structure information is indispensable. Canopy height acts
69 as the critical third dimension, serving as a robust allometric proxy for stem volume and biomass that remains
70 sensitive even in dense, multi-layered canopies where optical indices plateau.

71

72 This need for vertical structure information is increasingly being met by advanced spaceborne technologies.
73 The integration of observations from NASA's Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) and ICESat-
74 2 has emerged as a promising approach for forest structure applications (Potapov et al., 2021; Lang et al., 2023,
75 Lin et al., 2023). To maximize the utility of these height metrics, recent studies emphasize the synergistic
76 fusion of GEDI and ICESat-2 structural products with multispectral time-series data, such as Sentinel-2.
77 Applying advanced deep learning and machine learning frameworks to these fused datasets has demonstrated
78 superior capability in characterizing complex canopy conditions and mapping large-scale forest disturbances
79 (Ma et al., 2025). GEDI's ability to provide direct measurements of forest vertical structure has enabled the
80 development of global canopy height models (CHMs) that capture the three-dimensional complexity of forest
81 ecosystems with unprecedented accuracy. Beginning with the foundational work of Potapov et al. (2021), the
82 field has witnessed remarkable progress, with subsequent developments by Lang et al. (2023), Pauls et al.
83 (2025), and Tolan et al. (2024) pushing the boundaries of satellite-based height estimation.

84

85 Despite the proliferation of these global CHMs, several critical knowledge gaps limit their operational
86 application for national forest inventories. First, comparative evaluations of different CHMs against
87 comprehensive field datasets are rare, making it difficult for practitioners to select optimal products for specific
88 regions like Eastern Europe. Second, while individual studies have demonstrated the value of combining height
89 information with optical or radar data, systematic evaluations of different sensor combinations are lacking.
90 This gap is particularly important for operational applications where practitioners need guidance on optimal
91 data fusion strategies to maximize accuracy while minimizing computational complexity.

92

93 This study addresses these gaps through a comprehensive evaluation framework that advances satellite-based
94 forest inventory in Ukraine. Our primary objectives are to:

95

96 1) Systematically evaluate and compare six state-of-the-art continental-scale CHMs against extensive
97 field measurements from Ukraine's NFI to identify the most suitable height predictor.

98

99 2) Quantify the added value of satellite-derived canopy height for forest parameter estimation by
100 comparing models with and without CHM information.

101

102 3) Assess the scalability and transferability of the developed approach. This involves validating the
103 performance of a unified national-scale model against regionally specific sub-models and
104 demonstrating the feasibility of monitoring forest resources using exclusively publicly available
105 datasets with global coverage, thereby ensuring the method's applicability beyond the specific study
106 area.

107 **2. Material and Methods**

108 **2.1. Area Selection and Forest Inventory Data**

109 The study was conducted across two contrasting Ukrainian oblasts: Ivano-Frankivsk in western Ukraine and
110 Sumy in northeastern Ukraine (Figure 1). These regions were selected to represent the diverse forest conditions
111 across Ukraine, encompassing different climatic zones, topographic conditions, and forest types that are
112 representative of the country's forest resources.

113

114 Figure 1. The study area and distribution of NFI plots

115

116 Ivano-Frankivsk oblast (13,928 km²) is in the Carpathian region and characterized by complex mountainous
 117 topography with elevations ranging from 200 to 2,061 m above sea level. The region experiences a temperate
 118 continental climate with high precipitation (800–1,400 mm annually) and supports predominantly montane
 119 forests dominated by Norway spruce (*Picea abies* L.), silver fir (*Abies alba* L.), with European beech (*Fagus*
 120 *sylvatica* L.), and broadleaved forest composed by common oak (*Quercus robur* L.), linden (*Tilia cordata*

121 Mill.), ash (*Fraxinus excelsior* L.), and hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.) at lower elevations. Forest cover in
122 this oblast exceeds 40%, making it one of Ukraine's most forested regions.

123

124 Sumy oblast (23,832 km²) represents two other ecozones of Ukraine with relatively high forest cover, namely
125 Polissia and Forest-Steppe. The region is characterized by relatively flat terrain with elevations approximately
126 200 m a.s.l. The climate is temperate continental with moderate precipitation (500–600 mm annually). The
127 forest in the northernmost part (Polissia) mainly consists of pure Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) plantations,
128 while in the Forest-Steppe it predominantly has mixed composition with common oak and other deciduous
129 species such as linden, ash, Norway maple (*Acer platanoides* L.), birch, and aspen (*Populus tremula* L.). Forest
130 cover is approximately 25%, interspersed with agricultural lands.

131

132 Field data were obtained from Ukraine's NFI, which began systematic sampling in 2021 following international
133 standards and methodologies adapted from European NFI protocols. The NFI employs a systematic grid-based
134 sampling design with permanent circular plots (radius = 12.62 m, area = 500 m²) established at the intersections
135 of a 5 x 5 km grid across the country's forested areas. For this study, we utilized data from 2,634 NFI plots
136 (before outlier screening procedure) distributed across Ukraine, including 459 plots in Ivano-Frankivsk oblast
137 and 114 plots in Sumy oblast selected for detailed regional analysis. The temporal distribution of field
138 measurements spanned from 2021 to 2023, with most plots measured during the 2022–2023 field seasons. Each
139 plot provided comprehensive forest structure measurements including individual tree diameters at breast height
140 (DBH \geq 6 cm), tree heights, species identification, and age determinations through increment core analysis.

141

142 Four key forest inventory parameters were extracted for modeling:

- 143 ● Stand Age (years): Determined through increment core analysis of dominant trees, representing the average
144 age of the main canopy layer
- 145 ● Diameter at Breast Height (cm): Quadratic mean of all trees \geq 6 cm DBH within the plot
- 146 ● Growing Stock Volume (m³/ha): Total stem volume per hectare calculated using species-specific allometric
147 equations (Bilous et al., 2022; Myroniuk et al., 2022)
- 148 ● Basal Area (m²/ha): Sum of cross-sectional areas of all tree stems at breast height per hectare.

149

150 Canopy height measurements were obtained using Vertex IV hypsometers and clinometers, with the plot-level
151 canopy height defined as the mean height of the five tallest trees within each plot. This approach ensures
152 consistency with global canopy height model definitions while providing a robust representation of the
153 dominant canopy structure. Data quality control procedures included: (1) removal of plots with incomplete
154 measurements or measurement uncertainties >10%, (2) elimination of plots affected by recent disturbances
155 (harvesting, windthrow, fire within 2 years prior to measurement), and (3) exclusion of edge plots where forest
156 cover within the plot was <80% to minimize boundary effects.

157

158 **2.2. Remote Sensing Data Acquisition and Processing**

159 **2.2.1. Satellite Data Sources**

160 We integrated three complementary satellite data sources to characterize forest structure. Sentinel-2 Level-2A
161 surface reflectance data were acquired through Google Earth Engine (GEE) for the 2024 summer growing
162 season (June 1–August 31), utilizing nine multispectral bands spanning visible to shortwave infrared
163 wavelengths (490–2190 nm) at 20 m spatial resolution (see Table 1). Summer composites were specifically
164 selected to maximize vegetation signal quality while minimizing phenological variability and shadow artifacts.
165 Cloud screening combined the s2cloudless probability mask (30% threshold) with the Scene Classification
166 Layer to ensure robust artifact removal. Radar observations comprised both C-band and L-band datasets to
167 exploit their differential canopy penetration capabilities. Sentinel-1 Ground Range Detected products were
168 processed through GEE's standard pipeline, restricting analysis to descending orbit Interferometric Wide mode
169 acquisitions with VV and VH polarizations to maintain geometric consistency and minimize topographic
170 effects. Temporal aggregation to median values over the June–August 2024 window suppressed speckle noise
171 while preserving structural information. Complementing the C-band observations, ALOS PalsAR-2 annual
172 mosaics (2023) provided L-band backscatter in HH and HV polarizations at 25 m resolution. The longer L-
173 band wavelength (23.6 cm) enables deeper canopy penetration compared to C-band (5.6 cm), potentially
174 capturing sub-canopy structural elements critical for biomass estimation in dense forest stands. This multi-
175 sensor approach combines the synergistic information content of optical reflectance sensitive to canopy
176 biochemistry and phenology, C-band radar responsive to upper canopy structure and moisture, and L-band
177 radar characterizing total aboveground biomass through volume scattering mechanisms.

178

179 To ensure temporal consistency and minimize noise, we generated pixel-level median composites for all
 180 optical and radar datasets over the three-month summer window between June and August. All datasets
 181 underwent geometric harmonization through reprojection to WGS84 geographic coordinates (EPSG:4326) and
 182 resampling to a common 20 m spatial resolution using nearest-neighbor interpolation to preserve original pixel
 183 values. From the harmonized multisensory dataset, we extracted 18 predictor variables representing distinct
 184 biophysical and structural forest properties of NFI plots (Table 1).

Predictor	Data source
B2: Surface reflectance 490 nm	Sentinel-2
B3: Surface reflectance 560 nm	Sentinel-2
B4: Surface reflectance 665 nm	Sentinel-2
B5: Surface reflectance 705 nm	Sentinel-2
B6: Surface reflectance 740 nm	Sentinel-2
B7: Surface reflectance 783 nm	Sentinel-2
B8A: Surface reflectance 865 nm	Sentinel-2
B11: Surface reflectance 1610 nm	Sentinel-2
B12: Surface reflectance 2190 nm	Sentinel-2
Normalized Difference Vegetation index (NDVI, Rouse et al., 1973)	Sentinel-2
Normalized Difference Infrared Index (NDII, Hardisky et al., 1983)	Sentinel-2
Normalized Burn Ratio 2 (NBR2, Key & Benson, 2006)	Sentinel-2
Vertical/Vertical polarization C-band	Sentinel-1
Vertical/Horizontal polarization C-band	Sentinel-1
Ratio of VV/VH polarization	Sentinel-1
Horizontal/Horizontal polarization L-band	ALOS PalSAR-2
Horizontal/Vertical polarization L-band	ALOS PalSAR-2
Ratio of HH/HV polarization	ALOS PalSAR-2

199 Table 1. Remote sensing predictors used for the retrievals of forest inventory parameters.

201 2.3. Global Canopy Height Models

202 We systematically evaluated six state-of-the-art global canopy height models (CHMs) spanning 2021–2025,
 203 representing the development in satellite-based forest structure mapping (Table 2). These models reflect
 204 advances in three dimensions: spatial resolution (30 m to 1 m), algorithm development (traditional machine
 205 learning to self-supervised deep learning), and data fusion strategies (GEDI + optical/radar combinations).

Model	Resolution (m)	Nominal year(s)	Predictors	Algorithm
Potapov et al. (2021)	30	2019	GEDI + Landsat	Random Forest
Lang et al. (2023)	10	2020	GEDI + Sentinel-2	Probabilistic convolutional neural network
Liu et al. (2023)	3*	2023	GEDI + Planet	Unet convolutional neural network
Pauls et al. (2024)	10	2020	GEDI + Sentinel-2	Unet convolution convolutional neural
Pauls et al. (2025)	10	2019–2022	GEDI + Sentinel-2	Temporal convolution convolutional neural
Tolan et al. (2024)	1	2021	GEDI + WorldView	Vision transformers

207 Table 2. Six global canopy height models and their basic characteristics. *Please note that we accessed Liu et
208 al. (2023) as publicly available dataset with reduced 10 m resolution.

209

210 The evaluated CHMs include diverse technological productions. Potapov et al. (2021) established a framework
211 by fusing GEDI waveforms with Landsat time series through Random Forest regression, achieving global
212 coverage at 30 m resolution. Subsequent models leveraged higher-resolution optical data and advanced
213 algorithms: Lang et al. (2023) applied probabilistic convolutional neural networks to GEDI-Sentinel-2 fusion
214 at 10 m globally, while Liu et al. (2023) demonstrated 3 m capability over Europe using GEDI-PlanetScope
215 integration with airborne LiDAR for further calibrations (accessed at 10 m resolution for this study).

216 Recent innovations have focused on addressing GEDI's inherent geolocation uncertainty and temporal
217 dynamics. Pauls et al. (2024) introduced specialized loss functions to mitigate GEDI positional errors when
218 fusing with Sentinel-2 and SRTM elevation data. Their subsequent model (Pauls et al., 2025) demonstrated
219 multi-temporal height mapping (2019–2022) across Europe, enabling forest change detection. At the resolution
220 frontier, Tolan et al. (2024) achieved unprecedented 1 m global coverage through self-supervised learning with
221 vision transformers on GEDI-WorldView imagery pairs, albeit with limited temporal coverage.

222

223 Figure 2. Visual comparison of six global CHMs used in the study for the selected area of Ivano-Frankivsk
 224 oblast (24.6E, 48.6N).

225

226 To validate the models, we used standard regression metrics against NFI plot measurements. CHM values
 227 were extracted at plot center coordinates using each model's native resolution, with performance assessed
 228 through coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and
 229 relative RMSE ($rRMSE = RMSE/mean$, given in percentage unit). The optimal CHM, selected based on
 230 maximum R^2 and minimum RMSE, was integrated as a predictor in subsequent machine learning workflows,
 231 complementing the multispectral and radar feature set.

232

233 2.4. Feature Importance Selection and Model Training

234 All analyses were implemented in Python 3.12 using NumPy and Pandas for data manipulation, Scikit-learn
 235 for machine learning workflows, and specialized gradient boosting libraries (XGBoost, LightGBM). The
 236 computational workflow was executed on a standard office notebook computer equipped with an Intel Core
 237 i7-1365U processor (10 cores, 12 threads) and 32 GB RAM.

238

239 We assumed that the natural vertical increment of the forest stands over the 1–3-year interval is negligible, as
 240 it typically falls below the inherent uncertainty (RMSE) of the global CHM products. Nevertheless, to account
 241 for abrupt changes such as harvesting or disturbance, we applied an outlier detection procedure to remove
 242 observations with extreme residuals that likely correspond to structural changes during the intervening period.
 243 Statistical outlier detection employed the Interquartile Range (IQR) method, removing observations beyond
 244 $Q_1 - 1.5 \times IQR$ or $Q_3 + 1.5 \times IQR$ thresholds. This standard quality control procedure eliminated 3–5% of
 245 observations per variable. Feature standardization using zero mean and unit variance transformation ensured
 246 algorithmic comparability across distance-based and gradient-based methods. The final dataset comprised
 247 2,621 observations with complete predictor-response pairs across all forest inventory variables.
 248
 249 A comprehensive evaluation of 20 regression algorithms spanning eight methodological families was
 250 conducted to identify optimal approaches for forest parameter estimation (Table 3).

Algorithm Family	Algorithms	Count
Linear Models	Linear Regression, Ridge Regression, Lasso Regression, ElasticNet, Bayesian Ridge	5
Tree-based Ensembles	Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, AdaBoost, HistGradientBoosting, Bagging Regressor, Decision Tree	6
Advanced Gradient Boosting	XGBoost, LightGBM	2
Robust Regression	Huber Regressor, Theil-Sen Regressor, RANSAC Regressor	3
Instance-based Learning	k-Nearest Neighbors	1
Neural Networks	Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) Regressor	1
Support Vector Machines	Support Vector Regressor (SVR)	1
Gaussian Processes	Gaussian Process Regressor	1

251 Table 3. Regression algorithms evaluated across eight methodological families
 252 Hyperparameter optimization employed random search with cross validation with 100 iterations per algorithm,
 253 maximizing R^2 through 3-fold cross-validation. Model performance was evaluated using a 3-fold Cross-
 254 Validation (CV) framework to mitigate sampling bias and ensure every observation served as independent
 255 validation data. For each fold, hyperparameters were optimized via random search (100 iterations), and final
 256 metrics (R^2 , RMSE, rRMSE) were aggregated from the hold-out predictions to provide a robust estimate of

257 generalization error. This configuration balanced computational efficiency with robust performance estimation
258 given the dataset size. Algorithm-specific parameters were optimized within empirically determined ranges:
259 regularization strength (α : 10^{-4} to 10^2), ensemble size (50-500 estimators), tree depth (3-20 levels), and learning
260 rates (10^{-3} to 10^{-1}).

261

262 To quantify the added value of canopy height information for forest inventory mapping, we evaluated model
263 performance across seven predictor configurations. The baseline configuration used only spectral and radar
264 features (18 variables) without any height information. Subsequently, we enlarged this baseline with each of
265 the six global CHMs individually, creating seven distinct feature sets that allowed direct comparison of each
266 CHM's contribution to prediction accuracy. Use of the Random Forest algorithm allowed us to study the
267 importance of each predictor. For each configuration, the same Ridge Regression algorithm underwent
268 identical training and validation procedures, ensuring that performance differences reflected solely the quality
269 and information content of the integrated CHM rather than methodological variations. This systematic
270 approach enabled quantification of both the absolute improvement provided by height integration and the
271 relative performance hierarchy among contemporary global CHM products.

272

273 Two distinct modeling approaches were then evaluated for the best-performing set of predictors:

- 274 1) Country-wise models, that leveraged the full dataset ($n=2,634$) to maximize statistical power and
275 capture forest variability across ecological gradients
- 276 2) Regional models trained separately for Ivano-Frankivsk ($n=459$) and Sumy ($n=114$) oblasts to
277 optimize model performance for local forest conditions.

278

279 Wall-to-wall predictions were generated at 20 m resolution through tile-based processing (1000×1000 pixels
280 with 10% overlap) to accommodate memory constraints while preventing edge artifacts. For the top-
281 performing ensemble models, we quantified prediction uncertainty using the coefficient of variation (CV)
282 derived from the standard deviation of individual tree predictions, providing spatially explicit confidence
283 estimates essential for operational forest management decisions. The complete analytical workflow is
284 summarized in Figure 3.

285

286 Figure 3. Flowchart depicting the workflow of ML model training and validation.

287 **3. Results**

288 **3.1. Comparing Global Canopy Height Models Against NFI Reference Data**

289 The comparative evaluation of six global canopy height models (CHMs) against in-situ measurements from
 290 the Ukrainian NFI revealed substantial differences in performance across models. The Pauls et al. (2025)
 291 model demonstrated superior performance across both test regions, achieving the strongest correlation with
 292 ground truth measurements ($R^2 = 0.68$, RMSE = 4.65 m, MAE = 3.21 m). This represents a significant
 293 improvement over earlier generation models, with the Potapov et al. (2021) model showing substantially lower
 294 accuracy ($R^2 = 0.28$, RMSE = 7.58 m, MAE = 5.94 m). The performance hierarchy among the six models
 295 followed a consistent pattern: Pauls et al. (2025) > Liu et al. (2023) > Lang et al. (2023) > Pauls et al. (2024)
 296 > Tolan et al. (2024) > Potapov et al. (2021). The density scatterplots (Figure 4) reveal model-specific error
 297 patterns, with earlier models exhibiting heteroscedastic residuals and systematic underestimation in tall stands

298 (>30 m), while recent models maintain consistent accuracy across the full height range despite residual
299 saturation effects in the tallest canopies.

300
301 Figure 4. Accuracy assessment of canopy height models using Ukraine NFI data. Density scatterplots show
302 the agreement between predicted and observed heights, with the 1:1 line shown in red. Pauls et al. (2025)
303 outperformed other models, achieving the highest coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.68$) and lowest error
304 (RMSE=4.65 m).

305
306 **3.2. Feature Importance Analysis and Predictor Selection**

307 The Random Forest-based feature importance analysis revealed a clear order of predictor variables, with
308 the CHM-derived canopy height emerging as the main factor across all forest inventory parameters (Figure 5).
309 The Pauls et al. (2025) canopy height consistently ranked as the most influential predictor, accounting for
310 approximately 45-60% of the total feature importance depending on the target variable. It is worth noting that
311 this dominance of canopy height as the primary predictor was consistent across all six global CHMs evaluated,
312 regardless of their specific spatial resolution or underlying algorithm, although we present the detailed feature
313 importance analysis only for the best-performing product (Pauls et al., 2025).

314 Following canopy height, Sentinel-2 shortwave infrared (SWIR) bands (B12 and B11), demonstrated second
 315 highest importance. Notably, L-band radar backscatter from ALOS PalSAR-2 (HV and HH) ranked
 316 immediately after the SWIR bands, outperforming both C-band radar and most optical indices. Sentinel-1 (C-
 317 band) cross-polarized backscatter (VH) and co-polarized (VV) features also contributed to the model, ranking
 318 higher than the NDVI. While NDVI and NBR2 showed moderate importance, they were generally surpassed
 319 by the textural and structural information provided by the SAR datasets. Sentinel-2 visible bands (e.g. B2, B3,
 320 B4) exhibited the lowest importance scores across evaluated variables.

321

322

323 Figure 5. Feature importance of different predictors in the retrieval of Growing Stock Volume from a Random
 324 Forest algorithm (log scale). Canopy height model (here Pauls et al., 2025) was by far the most important
 325 predictor in modelling forest inventory parameters.

326

327 Guided by this feature importance analysis, we refined our predictor set for the final model training to include
 328 only the Sentinel-2 spectral reflectances and the Pauls et al. (2025) CHM. By excluding heterogeneous
 329 predictors that demonstrated marginal explanatory power (such as SAR backscatter), we aimed to construct a
 330 robust and generalized model architecture. This approach minimizes system complexity and mitigates the risk
 331 of error propagation inherent in fusing multi-sensor datasets with varying noise characteristics.

332

333 3.3. Machine Learning Model Performance and Algorithm Comparison

334 The systematic evaluation of 20 regression algorithms revealed consistent patterns in model performance
 335 across forest inventory variables. Ridge Regression emerged as the best-performing algorithm, achieving the
 336 balance between accuracy and generalizability (Table 4), though the top tier of algorithms exhibited
 337 remarkably similar accuracy, with R^2 values ranging narrowly from 0.54 to 0.55 among the ten best-performing
 338 methods. This convergence among linear models (Ridge, Linear Regression, Bayesian Ridge, Lasso) provides
 339 compelling evidence that the integration of high-quality CHM data essentially linearizes the relationship
 340 between remote sensing observations and forest inventory parameters. The marginal benefit of regularization
 341 (Ridge vs. ordinary least squares) was negligible ($<0.1\%$ R^2 improvement), indicating that multicollinearity,
 342 typically problematic in multispectral analysis, is effectively mitigated when structural height dominates the
 343 feature space.

344
 345 Tree-based ensembles demonstrated competitive but slightly inferior performance, with Random Forest
 346 achieving $R^2 = 0.549$ despite its theoretical advantages in capturing non-linear interactions. The modest
 347 performance differential suggests that any non-linearities in the predictor-response relationships are
 348 sufficiently weak that linear models can adequately approximate them. More concerning was the systematic
 349 underperformance of advanced gradient boosting implementations (XGBoost: $R^2 = 0.52$, LightGBM: $R^2 =$
 350 0.52), which fell 6% below linear models despite extensive hyperparameter optimization. This result likely
 351 reflects these algorithms' propensity to overfit subtle noise patterns in the training data that do not generalize
 352 to validation sets.

353

Model	Algorithm Family	MAE	R^2	rRMSE
Ridge Regression	Linear Models	22.644	0.552	11.596
Linear Regression	Linear Models	22.631	0.552	11.601
Bayesian Ridge	Linear Models	22.678	0.552	11.602
Lasso Regression	Linear Models	22.641	0.552	11.603
Random Forest	Tree-based Ensembles	22.363	0.549	11.615
Huber Regressor	Robust Regression	22.500	0.548	11.651
HistGradient Boosting	Tree-based Ensembles	22.791	0.543	11.702

Bagging Regressor	Tree-based Ensembles	22.571	0.541	11.719
Gradient Boosting	Tree-based Ensembles	22.794	0.538	11.774
RANSAC Regressor	Robust Regression	22.597	0.535	11.835
AdaBoost	Tree-based Ensembles	22.883	0.532	11.847
LightGBM	Tree-based Ensembles	23.242	0.521	11.976
XGBoost	Tree-based Ensemble	23.370	0.519	12.014
ElasticNet	Linear Models	25.700	0.461	12.757
k-Nearest Neighbors	Instance-based Learning	25.266	0.458	12.776
MLP Regressor	Neural Networks	24.894	0.410	13.311
Decision Tree	Tree-based Ensemble	28.039	0.281	14.682
Support Vector Regressor	Support Vector Machines	36.034	0.199	15.570
Gaussian Process	Gaussian Process	36.730	-0.729	22.714
TheilSen Regressor	Robust Regression	24.204	-1.918	25.998

354 Table 4. Average performance of different ML models for all forest parameters, dashed line – separation
355 between first ten best models used in Ensemble-modelling approach and the rest.

356

357 3.4 Forest Inventory Parameter Retrieval Performance

358 The comparison across different CHMs (Table 5) clearly demonstrates the value of using the most accurate
359 canopy height model available. The performance increase from no CHM to the best-performing CHM
360 represents a substantial improvement in remote sensing-based forest inventory capabilities, with average R²
361 improvements ranging from 49% (Basal Area) to 144% (DBH).

	No	Potapov et al.	Lang et al.	Liu et al.	Tolan et al.	Pauls et al.	Pauls et
	CHM	(2021)	(2023)	(2023)	(2024)	(2024)	al. (2025)
Age	0.24	0.28	0.38	0.37	0.31	0.38	0.49
DBH	0.18	0.21	0.31	0.29	0.25	0.3	0.44
GSV	0.36	0.4	0.45	0.49	0.46	0.52	0.64
BA	0.35	0.37	0.39	0.42	0.41	0.45	0.52

362

363 Table 5. Model performance (R^2 value) of best-performing Ridge Regression models with different predictors
364 of canopy height, ranging from no canopy height (No CHM) to a suite of six canopy height models used in the
365 study. Best values for each lines are highlighted with bold text. The ML model with Pauls et al. (2025) CHM
366 yielded the highest performance for all forest attributes, significantly increasing model performance, compared
367 to both No-CHM and other CHMs.

368

369 The models trained on the complete NFI dataset achieved significant accuracy across all four forest inventory
370 parameters when incorporating the Pauls et al. (2025) CHM (Figure 6). Growing Stock Volume showed the
371 highest prediction accuracy ($R^2 = 0.77$, RMSE = 86.13 m³/ha, rRMSE = 8.8%), followed by Basal area ($R^2 =$
372 0.68, RMSE = 7.40 m²/ha, rRMSE = 9.9 %), Stand age ($R^2 = 0.53$, RMSE = 17.17 years, rRMSE = 11.5%),
373 and Diameter at breast height ($R^2 = 0.48$, RMSE = 8.25 cm, rRMSE = 12.3%).

374

375 Figure 6. Density scatterplots visualizing the performance of ensemble of ten best models using Sentinel-1,
 376 Sentinel-2, PalSAR-2 and Pauls et al. (2025) canopy height model as predictors of Forest age (upper left),
 377 DBH (upper right), growing stock volume (lower left) and basal area (lower right) for all-available NFI plots.

378

379 Contrary to expectations, locally trained models demonstrated superior performance compared to the global
 380 model for most forest parameters, despite substantially smaller training datasets. The Ivano-Frankivsk local
 381 model (N = 459, Figure 7) achieved mixed results, with notable improvements in Forest age ($R^2 = 0.59$, +11%)
 382 and DBH ($R^2 = 0.64$, +33%) prediction, while showing reduced performance for GSV ($R^2 = 0.64$, -17%) and
 383 BA ($R^2 = 0.55$, -19%). The Sumy local model (N = 114, Figure 8) exhibited exceptional performance

384 improvements across nearly all parameters despite having the smallest training dataset. Age prediction
 385 improved dramatically ($R^2 = 0.71$, +34%), DBH showed remarkable enhancement ($R^2 = 0.81$, +69%), and both
 386 GSV ($R^2 = 0.79$, +3%) and BA ($R^2 = 0.70$, +3%) maintained or slightly improved accuracy. This superior
 387 performance of the Sumy model is particularly noteworthy given its limited sample size, suggesting that the
 388 relatively homogeneous forest conditions in the flat forest-steppe zone enable effective model calibration even
 389 with fewer training samples.

390
 391 Figure 7. Density scatterplots visualizing the performance of ensemble of ten best models using Sentinel-1,
 392 Sentinel-2, PalsAR-2 and Pauls et al. (2025) canopy height model as predictors of Forest age (upper left),

393 DBH (upper right), growing stock volume (lower left) and basal area (lower right) for Ivano-Frankivsk model
 394 using local NFI plots (N = 459).

395
 396 Figure 8. Density scatterplots visualizing the performance of ensemble of ten best models using Sentinel-1,
 397 Sentinel-2, PalSAR-2 and Pauls et al. (2025) canopy height model as predictors of Forest age (upper left),
 398 DBH (upper right), growing stock volume (lower left) and basal area (lower right) for Sumy model using local
 399 NFI plots (N = 114).

400

401 **3.5. Spatial Mapping and Regional Model Comparison**

402 The spatially explicit per-pixel maps generated for both study oblasts (Figure 9) reveal meaningful spatial
403 patterns that align with known forest distributions and management histories. The Ivano-Frankivsk oblast
404 shows higher GSV values in mountainous regions where mature coniferous forests dominate, while the Sumy
405 oblast displays a more heterogeneous pattern reflecting mixed forest composition and agricultural land use.
406 The accompanying coefficient of variation maps provides crucial uncertainty information, with CV values
407 typically ranging from 10–30% in core forest areas but exceeding 40% at forest edges and in topographically
408 complex terrain.

409

410 Figure 9. Per-pixel retrievals of growing stock volume for Ivano-Frankivsk (left) and Sumy (right) oblasts
 411 averaging outputs of ten best-performing machine learning models to yield their mean predicted GSV and
 412 coefficient of variation as quality layer of the retrieval.

413

414 The histograms of predicted GSV values (Figure 10) demonstrate realistic distributions with appropriate
 415 dynamic ranges for each region. Ivano-Frankivsk shows a broader distribution with higher maximum values
 416 (up to 400+ m³/ha), consistent with the presence of productive mountain forests. Sumy exhibits a more
 417 constrained distribution centered around lower values (modal class 50–100 m³/ha), reflecting the
 418 predominantly deciduous and mixed forest types characteristic of the forest-steppe zone.

419

420 Figure 10. Histograms of retrieved Growing stock volumes (top) and coefficients of variation (bottom) for
 421 Ivano-Frankivsk (left) and Sumy (right).

422

423 Direct pixel-by-pixel comparisons between globally and locally trained models reveal substantial differences
 424 in prediction patterns and accuracy (Figures 11-12). For Ivano-Frankivsk oblast, the global model shows
 425 systematic biases across all four forest parameters. Age predictions display considerable scatter (R² difference
 426 of ~0.1), with the global model underestimating ages in mature stands (>80 years) by 10-20 years. DBH

427 comparisons reveal even more pronounced differences, with the local model reducing prediction scatter by
 428 approximately 30% and eliminating the systematic underestimation of large-diameter trees (>40 cm) evident
 429 in the global model. For volume-related parameters (GSV and BA), however, the global model performs
 430 comparably or even slightly better, suggesting that volume allometry may be more consistent across regions
 431 than age-diameter relationships.

432
 433 Figure 11. Comparison of per-pixel retrievals of selected NFI variables of forested areas of Ivano-Frankivsk
 434 oblast of country-wise trained model (best performing Ridge regression, $N = 2,621$, x-axis) and local model
 435 (best performing Ridge regression, $N = 459$). Please note that negative values for growing stock volume and
 436 basal area are caused by non-forested pixels.

437

438 The Sumy oblast comparisons (Figure 12) demonstrate even more dramatic improvements with local
 439 calibration. The local model achieves remarkably tight correlations for all parameters, with particularly striking
 440 improvements for DBH (approaching $R^2 = 0.8$) and Age ($R^2 > 0.7$). The scatter plots reveal that the global
 441 model exhibits heteroscedastic errors that increase with parameter magnitude, while the local model maintains
 442 consistent prediction accuracy across the full range of values. This superior performance likely reflects the
 443 relatively homogeneous forest conditions in Sumy, where local calibration can effectively capture region-
 444 specific growth patterns without the confounding effects of diverse forest types.

445
 446 Figure 12. Comparison of per-pixel retrievals of selected NFI variables of forested areas of Sumy oblast of
 447 globally trained model (best performing Ridge regression, $N = 2,621$, x-axis) and local model (best performing
 448 Ridge regression, $N = 114$). Please note that negative values for growing stock volume and basal area are
 449 caused by non-forested pixels.

450 **4. Discussion**

451

452 Our study shows that by integrating recent global canopy height maps, models with multi-sensor satellite data
453 can achieve accuracy levels comparable to airborne LiDAR for forest inventory mapping. Our relative RMSE
454 values of 8.8–12.3% across four key forest parameters represent a significant advancement for satellite-based
455 approaches, particularly given the operational constraints in war-affected Ukraine (Myroniuk et al., 2024).
456 When evaluating six global CHMs, we found major performance differences, with Pauls et al. (2025) ($R^2 =$
457 0.68 , $RMSE = 4.65$ m) significantly outperforming earlier products like Potapov et al. (2021) ($R^2 = 0.28$).

458

459 The superior performance of Pauls et al. (2025) compared to Potapov et al. (2021) (R^2 increase of 0.4)
460 highlights the structural advantage of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) over pixel-based Machine
461 Learning. Potapov et al. rely on a Random Forest regressor at 30 m, which treats pixels independently. In
462 contrast, the CNN architecture used by Pauls et al. learns spatial context – interpreting textures, shadow
463 patterns, and canopy gaps – to infer height. Furthermore, the 30 m grid of Potapov et al. introduces significant
464 mixed-pixel effects in fragmented Ukrainian landscapes, whereas the 10 m resolution of Pauls et al. better
465 aligns with the typical crown dimensions of dominant trees.

466

467 The observed improvement of Pauls et al. (2025) over the (2024) version is attributed to the shift from static
468 to dynamic modeling. Pauls et al. (2024) primarily utilized static annual composites, which can be sensitive to
469 remnant cloud artifacts or phenological variability. The 2025 iteration incorporates dense Sentinel-2 time
470 series and improved temporal aggregation strategies. This allows the model to filter out seasonal noise (e.g.,
471 leaf-on/leaf-off variations) and focus on the persistent structural signal of the canopy, resulting in higher
472 consistency across diverse forest types.

473

474 Contraintuitively, the Very High Resolution (VHR) models – Liu et al. (2023) at 3 m and Tolan et al. (2024)
475 at 1 m –did not outperform the 10 m Sentinel-2 products. We attribute this to two converging factors:

476 1) VHR sensors (e.g., Planet, Maxar) typically offer limited spectral bands (RGB + NIR). They lack the
477 Shortwave Infrared (SWIR) and Red-Edge bands available on Sentinel-2 and Landsat. These bands are
478 physically linked to water content and lignocellulosic structure, providing critical proxies for biomass that
479 visible light cannot capture.

480 2) NFI plots represent an aggregate stand volume (12–25 m radius). Aggregating 1 m pixels to this scale
481 introduces high-frequency noise (e.g., intra-crown gaps, shadows) that 10 m pixels naturally smooth out.
482 Thus, 10 m resolution combined with rich spectral data appears to be the good combination for regional
483 inventory, balancing structural detail with spectral depth.

484

485 While the integration of the Pauls et al. (2025) canopy height model significantly improved predictive
486 performance, it is important to acknowledge that the relationship between the satellite-predicted heights and
487 the actual NFI field measurements contains substantial inherent error (RMSE = 4.65 m). Consequently,
488 utilizing these predicted heights as primary independent variables to map secondary forest parameters—such
489 as growing stock volume or basal area—inevitably propagates this initial structural uncertainty throughout the
490 machine learning framework. This limitation necessitates cautious interpretation of the derived wall-to-wall
491 maps, particularly at the individual pixel level, where local structural anomalies or prediction errors within the
492 foundational CHM may be magnified in the final inventory parameter estimates.

493

494 Our comprehensive evaluation of 20 algorithms yielded an unexpected result: linear models such as Ridge
495 Regression outperformed complex ensemble methods. This suggests that high-quality height information
496 linearizes forest parameter relationships and reduces the need for more complex nonlinear models. This
497 observation echoes earlier findings that simple statistical approaches often suffice when predictors are strong
498 and directly relevant (Fassnacht et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2019).

499

500 Feature importance analysis confirmed the dominant role of CHM-derived canopy height (45–60%), followed
501 by Sentinel-2 SWIR bands, are known to be sensitive to vegetation moisture content and canopy structure
502 (Schroeder et al., 2011). Notably, while radar backscatter (particularly L-band) demonstrated meaningful
503 predictive power, outperforming standard vegetation indices like NDVI, it remained secondary to the SWIR
504 bands. Consequently, we prioritized a predictor set based on the synergy between CHM and Sentinel-2,
505 selecting SWIR reflectances as the primary complement to height data. This approach benefit from on the
506 superior performance of SWIR in capturing canopy structure and moisture content while avoiding the
507 heterogeneity and processing complexity associated with integrating multi-modal SAR datasets.

508

509 To assess the uncertainty introduced by the temporal lag between the 2021 field measurements and the satellite
510 data, we conducted a sensitivity analysis comparing model performance across inventory years. While the
511 2023 subset demonstrated slightly higher explained variance for dynamic parameters like Growing Stock
512 Volume (R^2 of 0.66 vs. 0.59 for 2021), the difference in normalized RMSE was marginal ($< 2\%$). This indicates
513 that the temporal mismatch introduces minor aleatoric uncertainty rather than significant systematic bias.
514 Consequently, the 2021 data were retained to maximize the training sample size, ensuring the models
515 effectively capture the structural variability of the diverse forest landscapes.

516

517 The comparison between global and regional models revealed important operational insights. Local models
518 showed superior performance for structural parameters (Age: +11–34% R^2 ; DBH: +33–69% R^2), particularly
519 in the homogeneous forests of Sumy oblast. This finding underscores the role of local calibration in capturing
520 region-specific allometric relationships, consistent with earlier work showing that combining NFI and remote
521 sensing data improves precision (Tomppo et al., 2010; Wulder et al., 2020). However, national models
522 maintained acceptable accuracy and greater scalability, which is critical for broader applications such as
523 national reporting and climate assessments. A hybrid approach, using global CHMs as a baseline and locally
524 refining predictions where sufficient ground data exist, could provide the best balance between accuracy and
525 transferability.

526

527 The coefficient of variation maps provides essential operational guidance by highlighting prediction reliability
528 across landscapes. Higher uncertainties concentrate in topographically complex terrain (Ivano-Frankivsk) and
529 forest edges (Sumy), directly informing where field verification should focus. This aligns with global
530 experience from multi-sensor monitoring frameworks, where uncertainty mapping is increasingly emphasized
531 for transparency in operational inventories (Reiche et al., 2018).

532

533 Several technical limitations are worth considering. Height saturation above ~ 35 m affects mature stands,
534 potentially undervaluing carbon stocks. The 20-m resolution introduces mixed-pixel effects in fragmented
535 landscapes. Temporal mismatches between satellite data (2024) and field measurements (2021-2024) may
536 introduce errors in disturbed areas. However, these limitations must be contextualized: our accuracy levels fall

537 within operational tolerances for strategic (10–20% uncertainty) and tactical (15–25%) forest planning, with
538 only operational cruising requiring higher precision.

539

540 This work enhances the remote-sensing forest inventory that provided the first spatially explicit assessment of
541 forest resources in Ukraine in 2023 (Myroniuk et al., 2024). Similarly to earlier studies, we focused on
542 collecting continuously updated information on forest resources using freely available satellite data. This is
543 particularly important for the country affected by the war where large areas are inaccessible for field sampling.
544 According to Act No. 643-IX which was passed by the Parliament of Ukraine in 2020, the NFI was legally
545 recognised as a means of collecting national-scale forest information. Ukraine has adopted the best practice of
546 many European countries in establishing the NFI (Tomppo et al., 2010). However, the full potential of the
547 sample-based forest inventory could not be realised, as large areas were affected by the war or occupied by
548 Russia. From this perspective, a forest inventory based on remote sensing is the only feasible way to conduct
549 a forest inventory and assess the impact of the war on forests. This study therefore employed state-of-the-art
550 approaches combining NFI data obtained through sparse field sampling and mapping (Fassnacht et al., 2014;
551 Kangas et al., 2018; Lister et al., 2020). From a forest management perspective, this work is important because
552 it addresses the current need for forest resource assessment, which other approaches based solely on field
553 sampling cannot fulfil.

554

555 We demonstrated that canopy height models are a highly useful explanatory variable in machine learning
556 substantially improving the accuracy of previously published data (Myroniuk et al., 2024). Our study aimed
557 to leverage CH models for operational use in Ukraine, where resources for collecting direct canopy
558 measurements using aerial LiDAR scanning are limited. This ultimately guides the further development of the
559 methodology in areas contaminated by unexploded ordnance, where collecting field data is not a long-term
560 viable option. This research has many practical applications in the forest management of Ukraine including
561 state forest inventory, assessment of war-induced forest damage, improving forest monitoring capacity, and
562 supporting decision-making for post-war reconstruction. In practical terms, the presented approach has
563 significant potential for integration into Ukraine's forest management system and NFI, especially under current
564 wartime limitations on field access. The satellite-derived maps allow for the assessment of key forest structure
565 indicators, including growing stock, mean diameter, basal area, and stand age.

566

567 These products can support multiple NFI tasks. First, they allow the extrapolation of field-based NFI data
568 across the entire territory, including inaccessible regions. Second, satellite-based estimates can fill gaps in the
569 existing sample and improve the robustness of national reporting. Third, they provide spatial context for
570 targeted field validation, optimizing the allocation of field resources. Importantly, the ability to produce full-
571 coverage maps with per-pixel uncertainty enables transparent decision-making in planning, harvesting, and
572 forest restoration.

573

574 Beyond NFI support, the maps are directly applicable to forest management activities. They can assist in
575 identifying stands with high or low productivity, detecting forest disturbances (clear-cuts, degradation, fires),
576 and prioritizing areas for silvicultural interventions. These data also provide a robust input for national and
577 international reporting obligations under IPCC, FAO FRA, Forest Europe, and EU LULUCF regulation, as the
578 derived biomass can be translated into carbon stocks using standard conversion factors.

579

580 The achieved accuracies ($R^2 = 0.48\text{--}0.77$) match those considered operationally useful by national forest
581 inventories and exceed typical multispectral-only approaches (30–60% RMSE) by a factor of 3-5. Our findings
582 indicate a paradigm shift: the integration of global CHMs transforms satellite-based forest inventory from a
583 coarse supplementary tool to a primary operational method. For Ukraine, this enables monitoring continuity
584 despite the ongoing Russian aggression. For the global community, it demonstrates that operational forest
585 inventory is achievable now, without waiting for expensive infrastructure. As global CHMs continue
586 improving with ongoing GEDI collections and new missions like NISAR, satellite-based approaches may
587 eventually match or exceed traditional inventory methods in both accuracy and cost-effectiveness.

588 The methodological framework developed in this study represents several important innovations. The
589 systematic evaluation of six CHMs provides unprecedented insights into the performance characteristics of
590 current global height products, while the comprehensive machine learning evaluation offers practical guidance
591 for algorithm selection in operational applications. The integration of multiple satellite data sources through a
592 harmonized processing chain ensures reproducibility and scalability, while the comparison of global versus

593 regional modeling approaches addresses critical questions about the specificity-generalizability trade-off in
594 remote sensing applications.

595 Furthermore, this study contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting the complementary role of
596 satellite-based methods in forest inventory, which can enhance traditional field-based approaches by providing
597 more frequent and spatially comprehensive monitoring capabilities while maintaining the precision and
598 ground-truth validation that field measurements continue to provide. As global CHMs continue to improve
599 and new satellite missions become operational, the approaches developed here will become increasingly
600 valuable for supporting sustainable forest management and climate monitoring efforts worldwide.

601 **4. Conclusion**

602 This study demonstrates the operational viability of integrating global canopy height models with registered
603 optical and radar satellite data to overcome structural data gaps in national forest monitoring. Systematic
604 evaluation of six CHMs against Ukrainian NFI data identified the temporal convolutional neural network
605 approach (Pauls et al., 2025) as the most accurate structural predictor. Feature importance analysis confirmed
606 that derived canopy height dominates multispectral and backscatter signals, effectively linearizing the
607 relationship between remote sensing observations and forest inventory parameters. Consequently, regularized
608 linear algorithms such as Ridge Regression achieved optimal predictive performance, significantly
609 outperforming models relying exclusively on spectral data. Furthermore, while the national-scale framework
610 provides robust wall-to-wall baselines, local model calibration yielded marked improvements in parameter
611 retrieval, highlighting the importance of capturing region-specific allometric relationships. Ultimately, this
612 approach establishes a scalable, satellite-based forest inventory framework capable of delivering critical forest
613 structural parameters in data-scarce or structurally inaccessible environments.

614

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628

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